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Data Connector Report

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We thank the maintainers of the data connectors for their contribution to this report.

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What's new?

Added

- Editorial
- 2.1.25 TANGO Connector
- Appendix 3: RUN-DSP
- Appendix 4: DOME 4.0 IDS connector adaptor

Changed

- 1 Introduction (editorial changes)
- 2 Implementations of data connectors (editorial changes)
- Figure 3 Overview of connectors with up-to-date information.
- 2.1.7 ECI Gatewise IDS Connector powered by TNO
- 2.1.13 GATE Dataspace Connector
- 2.1.18 Mitsubishi Electric Dataspace Connector
- 2.1.21 Prometheus-X Dataspace Connector
- 2.1.23 soivity CaaS (Connector-as-a-Service)
- 2.1.24 soivity Open-Source EDC Connector
- 2.1.27 Tekniker Dataspace Connector (previously named "Tekniker IDS Connector")
- 2.1.28 Telekom DIH Connector
- 3 Additional initiatives and promising emerging solutions
- 4 Other technologies contributing to trustworthily share data (Editorial changes)
- 5 Conclusion
- Figure 5 Data connector development streams
- Figure 6 Number of connector variants
- Appendix 2: Ocean Provider

Removed

- None

Editorial

Dear Reader,

You have reached the final issue of the *Data Connector Report*. We invite you to look back with us on the journey we have taken. Over the past two years across 16 issues, we've explored the intricate world of connectors in data spaces. Our mission has been twofold: (1) to explain what data connectors are and why they are crucial in data spaces; (2) to shed light on the diverse array of connectors available, emphasizing their unique value propositions, adoption stories, and evolving features.

A Retrospective

The *Data Connector Report* has successfully fulfilled its purpose. From November 2022 to September 2024, our readers have gained insights into the latest developments, empowering informed decisions and driving innovation.

The Dataspace Protocol: A crucial milestone

A significant achievement in the data space community was reached in March 2024, with the release of the stable version of the Dataspace Protocol (DSP). This milestone represents a pivotal achievement within the data space community. The Dataspace Protocol serves as foundation for ensuring interoperability, bridging different systems, and unlocking the full potential of data sharing. As we approach the end of the year, the DSP is on track to become an international standard, marking an unprecedented achievement for the entire data space ecosystem¹.

Testing Compatibility: The TCK

Compliance with the Dataspace Protocol will be guaranteed by a Technology Compatibility Kit (TCK), currently in development as part of the Eclipse Dataspace Protocol specification project called Eclipse Dataspace TCK. The TCK includes test cases designed to validate compliance with the specification document.

Connectors that successfully undergo TCK testing will demonstrate their adherence to the DSP, instilling confidence in users and promoting seamless integration.

Looking ahead: the Data Space Connector Report

As we bid farewell to the *Data Connector Report*, a new chapter awaits. Starting in November 2024, IDSA will introduce the *Data Space Connector Report*. This new edition will focus exclusively on connectors that support the Dataspace Protocol. It will serve as the authoritative resource – a single point of truth – for information about connectors for data spaces that support the Dataspace Protocol and have been successfully tested via the TCK. Published regularly by the IDSA, this new report will be essential reading for those following the evolution of data spaces technology and looking to participate in the data spaces journey.

¹ More information in the IDSA Paper "Making the Dataspace Protocol an international standard" (July 2024): <https://internationaldataspaces.org/standardizing-the-dataspace-protocol/>

The IDSA team would like to extend heartfelt thanks to all the contributors and supporters of this publication. We look forward to exploring the next era of data spaces with you.

1 Introduction

1.1 The data connector report

The *Data Connector Report* is a key publication from IDSA, designed to clarify the topic of data connectors. This report serves as a comprehensive guide, addressing various aspects of data connectors and their role in data spaces.

In particular, the Report:

- explains the importance of data connectors, including what they are and why they are a key element in data spaces.
- describes the main four typologies of connectors (data connector frameworks, open-source generic solutions, proprietary generic solutions, off-the-shelf data connectors or connectors integrated in data-related products)
- summarizes the necessary requirements to make data connectors interoperable and highlights the importance of a protocol agnostic standard, like the Dataspace Protocol.
- provides visibility to existing connector implementations, offering details such as license type, maturity, adoption cases, while tracking their evolution over time.
- serves as a reference point for learning and fostering interoperability in data sharing ecosystems, providing an overview of additional existing solutions that enable data sharing in data-driven business ecosystems, with the aim of fostering future alignment with IDS.
- lists additional technologies (e.g. Gaia-X trust framework, iShare, SOLID...) that contribute to trustworthy data sharing in data spaces.

Please note that the *Data Connector Report* focuses on these topics. For details on IDS use cases or deployment scenarios, refer to complementary IDSA resources:

- for use cases:
 - o Please refer to the Data Spaces Radar², an interactive tool launched in January 2024. by IDSA in the context of the Data Spaces Support Center (DSSC)³. This tool offers an overview and quick information on various data spaces initiative and use cases, highlighting their different implementation stages, domains and providing several additional details. The information is regularly updated by IDSA within the Data Spaces Support Centre project.
 - o additional details on IDS-based use cases are available in the Data Spaces Radar Brochure, downloadable from the IDSA Website⁴
- For deployment scenarios:

² <https://www.dataspaces-radar.org/radar/>

³ <https://dssc.eu/>

⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/most-important-documents/>

- visit the Deployment Scenarios section on the IDSA GitHub⁵. Here you can find technical descriptions of how a component, or a set of components has been deployed. You can also submit a request to add a deployment scenario, in case you wish to share your implementation work. This content is also available in a more user-friendly format in the IDS Knowledge Base⁶.

1.2 Why do we need data connectors?

Data connectors are essential for sharing data because they enable secure and effective communication and exchange in data spaces. They are a critical tool to connect many data endpoints, increasing the pool of accessible data and accelerating the data economy. By using data connectors, data spaces become protected environments where participants can share data freely, with rules ensuring data sovereignty, transparency and fairness. The data connectors serve as nodes in a data space and provide data sovereignty by design. This Report focuses specifically on data connectors for data spaces.

While data sharing and exchange are not new concepts, their requirements are constantly evolving. A data connector provides two key functionalities:

1. **Data exchange services:** serve as the Application Programming Interface (API) to other participants in a data space to achieve interoperability.
2. **Trustworthy data handling:** implementing policy enforcement mechanisms and a common baseline for cybersecurity.

As data varies and the requirements for data sharing differ, there are multiple types of connectors needed (see the IDS RAM section 2.2⁷ and section 2.4⁸ for more information). This Report provides an overview of these data connectors, their purpose, use and distinctions.

The figure below shows the diversity of requirements in industrial ecosystems. A data connector for (I)IoT devices may have substantially different requirements (in terms of resource consumption, efficiency, and cyber security), than a connector of a data marketplace or an industrial cloud platform. Despite these differences, such services must seamlessly integrate open data. A data connector will enable interoperability and will put data to use, to link it with other data and to support modern concepts such as shared and distributed digital twins, AI, or federated learning. To achieve this, connectors employ archetypical patterns for management service, orchestrate cloud-based service, lightweight API gateways or IoT gateways. They may use concepts like distributed ledgers, but they will rely on state-of-the-art data management capabilities.

⁵ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-Deployment-Scenarios>

⁶ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-deployment-scenarios>

⁷ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-ram-4/context-of-the-international-data-spaces/2_1_data-driven-business_ecosystems/2_2_data_sovereignty_as_a_key_capability

⁸ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-ram-4/context-of-the-international-data-spaces/2_1_data-driven-business_ecosystems/2_4_data_exchange_and_data_sharing

Figure 1 International data spaces connecting different clouds, on-premises applications, devices, marketplaces, and open data in an industrial scenario.

While the requirements for data sovereignty, i.e. the ability to express and enforce rights and obligations, are different in such scenarios, a need for basic interoperability is fundamental for data connectors to build interoperable data spaces.

1.3 What is a data connector?

Data connectors are crucial for fostering trust and interoperability in data sharing and exchange within data spaces. Data sovereignty, the cornerstone of data spaces, will form the level playing field on a global scale. This represents a significant advantage and revolutionizes the data economy of the future – with the goal of benefiting society, businesses, and individuals.

New data spaces may have different implementations and standards, which can lead to the creation of new data silos. Therefore, a strong push for convergence is necessary to ensure interoperability, data continuity, and common governance models that support data sovereignty for all data spaces. The IDSA Rulebook⁹ provides an overview of the functional requirements of a data space, the fundamental structure and introduces the mandatory and optional functionalities of a data space.

The core mission of the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) is to develop and maintain a reference architecture for data sharing and exchange that prioritizes data sovereignty in data-driven business ecosystems. The IDSA has created guidelines and a reference architecture model (RAM)¹⁰ that facilitates secure and self-determined data sharing between trusted parties across various ecosystems.

Certified users in a data space can attach usage restriction policies to their data before making it available to other participants. The IDS Connector is a central component of the

⁹ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-rulebook>

¹⁰ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-ram-4/introduction/1_1_goals_of_the_international_data_spaces

IDS standard and enables data exchange services as described in the IDS-RAM section 3.5.2¹¹ (see also figure below). It uses container technology to ensure "trusted execution", meaning the data within the container is always protected from unauthorized access and manipulation. The Dataspace Protocol¹², introduced in stable version in March 2024¹³, is mandatory for all data connectors to ensure interoperability and will be later on included in the IDS Certification.

Launched in 2022, the IDS Certification¹⁴ proves compliance with the IDS requirements defined by the IDSA Certification Working Group. It offers different trust and assurance levels for both connectors and operational environments. Before its launch, pre-certification (IDS-Ready) was available to support companies in preparing for certification via a third-party assessment.

The IDS standard addresses technical, operational, and legal agreements in data spaces¹⁵, which combine technical, organizational, and legal complexities. It provides guidelines for data sharing and adds features such as identity management, communication security, and usage control. The IDS Connector is defined in DIN SPEC 27070 as part of the German standardization work and subject to international standardization in ISO/IEC, CEN/CENELEC, IEEE, and W3C.

Implementations of data connectors based on the IDS standard are available as closed- and open-source software. Regarding the latter, the IDSA has developed the IDS Graduation Scheme¹⁶, which provides a set of rules, processes, and criteria to manage these open-source implementations on the IDSA GitHub¹⁷.

¹¹ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-ram-4/layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3-layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3_5_0_system_layer/3_5_2_ids_connector#ids-connector-functionalities

¹² <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/dataspace-protocol>

¹³ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-releases-stable-version-of-the-dataspace-protocol/>

¹⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/use/certification/>

¹⁵ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/rule-book-on-structures-and-processes-for-implementing-ids-in-the-real-world/>

¹⁶ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/idsa/tree/main/graduation_scheme

¹⁷ [International-Data-Spaces-Association/idsa: This is the main repository of International Data Spaces Association on GitHub, where you can find general overview and useful information on IDS Landscape.](https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/idsa)

Figure 2 Data Exchange Services realized by a data connector as described in the IDS-RAM section 3.5.2

1.4 Interoperability of data connectors

Technical Interoperability is a critical requirement in data spaces. It should be realized by data connectors, based on specifications and standards rather than singular or reference implementations. This requires addressing multiple levels of interoperability, including: first, the general interaction between the connectors for the description of data assets and the related endpoints must be addressed including the definition of policies for access control and usage control, followed by the negotiation of those policies and contracts. The initiation and management of the data exchange process needs a clear specification, which can be mapped then to tangible protocols, like https, MQTT, web sockets or others. This is the handover to use case specific, domain-specific or ecosystem-specific definitions and standards.

General interactions require a robust standard that can be implemented by the different connectors, while the subsequent data exchange makes use of domain or use case-specific standards. The same applies to semantic interoperability, which can be achieved on the foundation of the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)¹⁸. The further definition of the data exchanged is handled by semantic models, taxonomies, schemas or other similar mechanisms, the so-called “vocabularies”.

For robust and reliable data spaces, connector interoperability must be continuously verified against established standards and specifications. This ensures the robustness of data sharing, along with ongoing management and verification of security aspects related to the data connectors.

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

Current usable standards already support the goals of interoperability, but additional standards are required. The interaction of the connectors on the general level as depicted in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** requires a protocol agnostic standard as a foundation for interoperable data spaces. IDSA is working on a specific **Dataspace Protocol**¹⁹, a set of specifications designed to facilitate interoperable data sharing between entities governed by usage control and based on web technologies. These specifications define the schemas and protocols required for entities to publish data, negotiate usage agreements, and access data as part of a federation of technical systems termed a data space. The Dataspace Protocol, therefore, represents the foundation for technical interoperability in data spaces: every data connector used in a data space must implement the Dataspace Protocol. IDSA released the stable version of the Dataspace Protocol 2024-1 in March 2024²⁰. The Dataspace Protocol will become an ISO standard. To know more about its path towards standardization, check out the IDSA Paper “Making the Dataspace Protocol an international standard” (July 2024)²¹.

1.5 The relation of data connector solutions and frameworks

Data connectors differ across multiple dimensions, but they can generally be grouped into four main categories: data connector frameworks, open-source generic solutions, proprietary generic solutions and off-the-shelf data connectors. Detailed explanations are provided below.

- **Data connector frameworks:** These are modular data space components used as the foundation for implementing data connectors. Most frameworks are available as free and open-source software (FOSS). Developers can build solutions by extending these frameworks. Examples include Eclipse Data Space Components, the FIWARE ecosystem (including the TRUE Connector) and the IDS Messaging Library²². These frameworks are designed for developers rather than end-users, meaning they require additional development work to share and consume data.
- **Generic open-source solutions:** These solutions provide data connectors that can be integrated directly into an IT landscape and connected to services. They often act as proxies or gateways to an organization’s IT services. Configuring the components and adding custom extensions is typically required to share and consume data. The Data Space Connector and the TNO Secure Gateway are good examples of such connectors. Some connectors mentioned later in this Report build on and extend generic open-source solutions to provide additional generic open-source solutions or proprietary software.
- **Proprietary generic solutions:** These are offered by companies and organizations as proprietary software for generic usage. Like their open-source counterparts, they typically require additional configuration and extension to meet specific needs. An example is the nicos GAIABOX connector.
- **Off-the-shelf solutions:** These connectors are ready-to-use, either as a service or as a product that can be directly integrated into an IT system with minimal configuration.

¹⁹ Github: <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/dataspace-protocol/overview/readme>.

²⁰ News article: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/idsa-releases-stable-version-of-the-dataspace-protocol/>

²¹ IDSA Paper: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/standardizing-the-dataspace-protocol/>

²² IDS Messaging Services: <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-Messaging-Services>

While some adaptation to a company's IT environment is still necessary, these solutions significantly reduce the effort required compared to more customized options. One example is the connector-as-a-service offered by soivity. In extension to such data connector offerings, this Report also includes connectors which are already integrated into data-related products, like the Data Intelligence Hub and the Tech2B Connector.

2 Implementations of data connectors

This section brings clarity on the implementations of IDS data connectors. It provides a clear structure for describing them, offering an overview of some of the existing solutions and detailed descriptions for each of them. Please note that the provided overview is not exhaustive.

To provide a clear mapping of existing connectors, an effective structure of the information is necessary. For this reason, some existing scientific work and, specifically, the following paper: Gieß, A., Hupperz, M., Schoormann, T., Möller, F. (2024): What Does it Take to Connect? Unveiling Characteristics of Data Space Connectors. In Proceedings of the 57th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS), Honolulu, Hawaii, USA²³. The paper has been leveraged to create a new ad-hoc structure to collect and report detailed information on each connector. This maps both general information on the connector and its adoption (e.g. name, maintainer, short description, example of applications of the connector...) going deeper into technical features (e.g. deployment options, protocol supported, integration with other components...). Please note that to facilitate the description of some features, some options are provided, but do not aim to be exhaustive.

The structure based on which each connector can be described, is explained below.

- *Connector Overview*
 - o Name of the connector
 - o Maintainer (company name)
 - o Peculiarity of the connector, i.e. short description, describing Unique Selling Point and/or main field of application of the connector (for example: cloud, IoT,..)
 - o More information (e.g. links for further deep-dive)
- *Connector Details*
 - o Type of connector, based on the description on paragraph 1.5, i.e.:
 - A data connector framework (i.e. modular data space components to be used as a basis to implement a data connector)
 - A generic open-source solutions (i.e. data connectors that can be integrated directly into an IT-Landscape and connected to services, often acting as proxies or gateways to companies' IT-Services)
 - A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions)
 - An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
 - An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
 - o Maturity of the connector. The maturity level can be described with different indicators based of your preference. Examples of indicators are the levels of the IDS Graduation Scheme²⁴, IDS Certification²⁵, TRL;

²³ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374169204_What_Does_it_Take_to_Connect_Unveiling_Characteristics_of_Data_Space_Connectors

²⁴ https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/idsa/tree/main/graduation_scheme

²⁵ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/certification/>; TRL: https://www.nasa.gov/directorates/heo/scan/engineering/technology/technology_readiness_level

- Portability, i.e. existing dependencies to the environment:
 - Agnostic (e.g. platform agnostic: the connector can be hosted on various cloud environments)
 - Specific (e.g. operating-system specific, e.g. only Linux)
- License type, i.e. availability of the code:
 - Open source (i.e. without restrictions, e.g., Apache 2.0)
 - Open source - copyleft (i.e. free, but requiring that all modified and extended versions of the program also be free)
 - Closed source - extendable (i.e. extensions permitted)
 - Closed source (i.e. source text is not publicly viewable)
- IDS Certification
- Adoption examples, i.e. existing cases of applications of the connector, to give visibility to the projects where the connector is implemented.
- Deployment options, i.e. for example:
 - Edge (e.g. manufacturing units, smartphones)
 - On-premises (e.g. local server)
 - Cloud (e.g. Microsoft Azure, AWS)
 - IoT/CPS/OT devices
- Service level, i.e. effort required to deploy a connector
 - Connector as a service (i.e. SAAS, plug-and-play solution)
 - Platform as a service (i.e. configuration)
 - Self-service (i.e. all self-made, e.g. by using an established framework like the EDC)
- *Access and usage control*
 - Access control, i.e. how the interception of data processing and prohibition of data access is managed
 - OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs)
 - Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
 - API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
 - Usage control, i.e. technical enforcement of usage restrictions. More info on data usage control is provided in the IDSA Position Paper "Data Usage Control in IDS"²⁶.
 - Types of policies supported (if usage control is ensured), based on the IDS policy classes. More information on the IDSA GitHub²⁷.
- *Communication*
 - Communication protocol, i.e. how is the connection between two electronic devices for data exchange enabled?
 - IDS Multipart
 - IDS Communication Protocol (IDSCP)
 - IDS-REST

²⁶ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/data-sovereignty-updated-position-paper-on-data-usage-control-in-the-ids/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-G/tree/main/UsageControl/Contract#policy-classes>

- Dataspace Protocol (HTTPS)
- Dataspace Protocol (other binding)
- Transfer protocol, i.e. how the data from different databases is indexed and retrieved. More information in the IDS RAM section 3.4.4²⁸
 - In-band with determined protocol bindings
 - In-band with not determined protocol bindings
 - Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added)
 - Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
- *Graphical user interface*, i.e. any GUI of computer systems facilitating operation
 - No (i.e. the connector can only be used via command line or operator needs to develop their own GUI)
 - Graphical user interface for users
 - Graphical user interface for management
 - Graphical user interface for administration
- *Identity management*, i.e. Participant information based on organizational assessment
 - Centralized (X.509)
 - Decentralized (did:web)
 - Decentralized (SSI)
 - None
- *IDS Information Model* and, in case, version supported. More information on the IDSA GitHub²⁹
- *Vocabulary supported*, e.g. a domain specific vocabulary
- *Integration with additional components* and, in case, version supported:
 - Catalogue / Broker
 - Clearing House

IDSA is constantly collecting and updating information on various connector implementations. This version of the Connector Report offers a detailed updated description of 34 connectors, based on the above-mentioned structure, which was provided by the maintainers after August 2023. In addition, four other connectors are also listed in 2.2 Connectors with latest updates in May 2023, based on information provided in May 2023 or before. In total, 38 connectors are described in this Report.

2.1 Connectors with up-to-date information

This paragraph provides detailed information on 34 connectors which have been described based on the structure defined in 2 Implementations of data connectors. The information was provided after August 2023.

²⁸ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4/layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3-layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3_4_process_layer/3_4_4_exchanging_data

²⁹ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/InformationModel>

An overview of the connectors is provided in Figure 3 Overview of connectors with up-to-date information.. All details are described in the course of this chapter.

Connectors with up-to-date information							
Section	Name of connector	Maintainer	Open source	IDS certified	Identity management	Deployment options	Service level
2.1.1	Advaneo Open-Source EDC Connector		✓		X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	Self-service
2.1.2	Advaneo-X Connector				X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS Self-service
2.1.3	Advaneo Trusted Connector				X.509	Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS
2.1.4	AI.SOV Connector					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud 	Platform-aaS
2.1.5	Boot-X Connector						Connector-aaS
2.1.6	Data Space Integration				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X.509 didweb SSI 	Cloud	Platform-aaS
2.1.7	ECI IDS Connector powered by TNO				X.509	Cloud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Self-service
2.1.8	Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC)		✓			Not specified	Service level is best effort of the open-source-community
2.1.9	EdgeDS Connector		✓			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud IoT/CPS/OT 	Connector-aaS
2.1.10	EGI Datahub Connector		✓		X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	Platform-aaS
2.1.11	EONA-X EDC Connector		✓		didweb	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Self-service
2.1.12	FIWARE Data Space Connector		✓		X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Self-service
2.1.13	GATE Dataspace Connector		✓	✓	X.509	On-premises	Platform-aaS
2.1.14	GDSO Connector - Tyre Information Service		Partially		AWS Cognito	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud IoT/CPS/OT 	Platform-aaS
2.1.15	HEALTH-X dataLOFT EDC				SSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Self-service
2.1.16	IIOC (Intel IONOS Orbiter Connector)		✓		SSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cloud IoT/CPS/OT 	
2.1.17	Kharon IDS Connector				Kharon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS
2.1.18	Mitsubishi Dataspace Connector		Partially			IoT/CPS/OT	Self-service
2.1.19	MPAD-C by Mondragon				X.509	On-premises	Self-service

Connectors with up-to-date information							
Section	Name of connector	Maintainer	Open source	IDS certified	Identity management	Deployment options	Service level
2.1.20	OneNet Connector		✓		X.509	On-premises	Connector-aaS
2.1.21	Prometheus-X Dataspace Connector		✓		did:web	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS
2.1.22	Silicon Economy EDC		✓			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud IoT/CPS/OT 	Self-service
2.1.23	sovity CaaS (Connector-as-a-Service)				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X.509 did:web SSI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud Others 	Connector-aaS
2.1.24	sovity Open-Source EDC Connector		✓		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X.509 Mock IAM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud Others 	Self-Hosted
2.1.25	TANGO Connector		Partially		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> did:web SSI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	Platform-aaS
2.1.26	Tech2B SCSN Connector				did:web	Cloud	
2.1.27	Tekniker Dataspace Connector		✓		SSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud Edge 	Connector-aaS
2.1.28	Telekom DIH Connector			✓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X.509 did:web 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	Connector-aaS
2.1.29	TNO Security Gateway (TSG)		✓	✓	X.509	Cloud	Self-service
2.1.30	Tritom Enterprise Connector					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	Platform-aaS
2.1.31	TRUE Connector		✓	✓	X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud IoT/CPS/OT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS Self-service
2.1.32	Trusted Connector		✓		X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud 	Platform-aaS
2.1.33	Trusted Supplier Connector (TSC)					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edge On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS Self-service
2.1.34	VTT DSIL Connector			✓	X.509	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-premises Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector-aaS Platform-aaS

Figure 3 Overview of connectors with up-to-date information.

2.1.1 Advaneo Open-Source EDC Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Advaneo Open Source EDC Connector
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer	Advaneo GmbH
Peculiarity of the connector	Introducing a fully operational open-source connector designed to facilitate seamless data sharing among data space participants, incorporating advanced usage control and enhanced usability features. This connector integrates an API abstraction layer that offers superior endpoints for workflows, significantly improving performance over the standard EDC Management API.
More Information	-

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solution
Maturity	TRL 6 - system/subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment (ground or space)
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2.0) ³⁰
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Green Deal Dataspace³¹ » PAIRS³² project » Resilience Mesh³³
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)

³⁰ The link to the repository will be provided in the next versions of this Report.

³¹ <https://green-deal-dataspace.eu/de/>

³² <https://www.pairs-projekt.de/de/>

³³ <https://green-deal-dataspace.eu/rd-projects/rd-resilience-mesh>

Support of usage control	No
Usage control policies	-
Communication	
Communication protocol	Dataspace protocol 2024-01 (HTTPS)
Transfer protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none">» Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added)» Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For users
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.2 Advaneo-X Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Advaneo-X Connector
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer	Advaneo GmbH
Peculiarity of the connector	Introducing a fully managed connector designed to facilitate seamless data sharing among data space participants, incorporating advanced usage control and enhanced usability features. It is based on EDC and interoperable with dataspaces like MDS, Catena-X, and others. Key feature is a runtime environment for applications or services consuming or producing data of data spaces.
More Information	

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions) » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL 4 - component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Green Deal Dataspace³⁴ » PAIRS³⁵ project » Resilience Mesh³⁶
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
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³⁴ <https://green-deal-dataspace.eu/de/>

³⁵ <https://www.pairs-projekt.de/de/>

³⁶ <https://green-deal-dataspace.eu/rd-projects/rd-resilience-mesh>

Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of usage control	No
Usage control policies	-

Communication

Communication protocol	Dataspace protocol 2024-01 (HTTPS)
Transfer protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added) » Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-

2.1.3 Advaneo Trusted Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Advaneo Trusted Connector
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Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer	Advaneo GmbH
Peculiarity of the connector	Data connector based on Trusted Connector of Fraunhofer AISEC adding an API abstraction layer that offers easy-to-use features for integrating various types of data sources and targets. It integrates with our data marketplace solution for monetization of data sets and our trusted data hub for secure multi-party computation.
More Information	
Connector Details	
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions) » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service » An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in a space environment
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source - extendable (i.e., extensions permitted)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Advaneo Trusted Data Hub³⁷ » Advaneo Data Marketplace³⁸
Deployment options	On-premises
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service
Access & Usage Control	
Access control	Yes
Type of access control	API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of usage control	No
Usage control policies	-
Communication	
Communication protocol	IDS Communication protocol (IDSCP)
Transfer protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

³⁷ <https://www.advaneo.de/en/trusted-data-hub-privacy-preserving-multi-party-computing/>

³⁸ <https://www.advaneo-datamarketplace.de/en/>

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For users

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-

2.1.4 AI.SOV Connector

Connector Overview

Name	AI.SOV Connector
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer	Cefriel
Peculiarity of the connector	The AI.SOV connector is built upon the Fraunhofer open connector plus a resources catalogue created by Cefriel leveraging the KCong asset. The asset obtained is a user-friendly data exchange platform for the supply chain domain compliant to the IDS data sovereignty concept.
More Information	AI.SOV GitLab ³⁹

Connector Details

Type	A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions)
Maturity	TRL7, used in data exchange domains
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source – extendable (i.e. extensions permitted)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The connector is used by both Whirpool and Sonae Arauco to share data with their supply chain. It has been used by another important automotive company to gather data from ologer trackers installed in their plants.
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » Basic Auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of usage control	Yes
Usage control policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer

³⁹ <https://gitlab.cefriel.it/groups/ai-sov>

» IDS Connector

Communication

Communication protocol	IDS protocol (IDSCP)
Transfer protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » For users » For management » For administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	No
Type	-

Information Model

IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	Version 4.1

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	A customized catalogue developed by Cefriel
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.5 Boot-X Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Boot-X Connector
Maintainer	Huawei, Munich Research Center
Logo of the connector or company logo	 HUAWEI
Peculiarity of the connector	The Boot-X is Gaia-X / IDSA compliance ready, cloud-based Data Space implementation. The main focus is on cross-border data exchange, e.g. following international standards for data exchange between Chinese and European industries. Boot-X Connector is compatible to Eclipse Data Space connector, with enhanced features like local data policy, Self-Sovereign identity federation and compliance monitoring.
More Information	Boot-X website ⁴⁰

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A data connector framework » A generic solutions software » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL 7
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open-source license not finally determined yet.
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Boot-X ⁴¹ is a Data Space platform for cross-border Data Exchange. The first use case is in supply chain management, but Boot-X itself is domain agnostic. Boot-X has been developed in Europe according to Gaia-X / IDSA standards. It is also interoperable with a Data Space service offered by Huawei Cloud in China, called EDS ("Exchange Data Service" ⁴²), to enable cross-border Data exchange between China and Europe.
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud » Huawei Cloud

⁴⁰ www.boot-x.eu

⁴¹ www.boot-x.eu

⁴² <https://www.huaweicloud.com/product/eds.html>

Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service
Access & Usage Control	
Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » via OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password) » API key (manage access through a unique code for programming interface) » SSI OIDC credential bridge is integrated in Boot-X
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » IDS Connector » Application inside a Connector » User Role » Time Interval » Duration » Location » Number of usage » Inform a participant about the Data Usage » Delete Data
Communication	
Communication protocol	Dataspace protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » In-band with determined protocol bindings » Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » For users » For management » For administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized (X.509) » Decentralized (did:web) » Decentralized (SSI) » Boot-X includes credential bridge for SSI and OIDC.
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker:	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	EDC Catalogue
Integration with Clearing House:	-
Clearing House type	-

2.1.6 Data Space Integration by SAP

Connector Overview

Name	Data Space Integration
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer	SAP SE
Peculiarity of the connector	<p>The Data Space Integration is embedded into SAP Integration Suite to leverage the full power of SAP's leading integration platform-as-a-service.</p> <p>It is based on the Eclipse Dataspace Components Connector, currently EDC 0.5.3</p>
More Information	More information on the SAP Integration Suite is available on the SAP website ⁴³

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions) » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL7
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source (SAP Integration Suite, standard edition)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The Data Space Integration is currently provided to selected customers via a beta program. SAP sales representatives can provide adoption examples
Deployment options	Cloud
Service level	Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » Basic Auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of usage control	No
Usage control policies	-

Communication

⁴³ <https://www.sap.com/germany/products/technology-platform/integration-suite.html>

Communication protocol	Dataspace protocol 0.8 (HTTPS)
Transfer protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » for users » for management » for administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized (X.509) » Decentralized (did:web) » Decentralized (SSI)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	Yes
Type of vocabulary provided	ODRL, DCAT, DSpace, Tractus-X
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	EDC's in-built catalogue
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.7 ECI Gatewise IDS Connector powered by TNO

Connector Overview

Name	ECI Gatewise IDS Connector powered by TNO
Maintainer	ECI Software Solutions and TNO
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	By using the cloud-based IDS connector, companies affiliated with a SCSN Service Provider can digitally exchange supply chain related messages with companies affiliated with another SCSN Service Provider.
More Information	TNO website on IDS technology ⁴⁴

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A data connector framework » A generic open-source solution » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL 9 (live)
Portability	Specific
License	The IDS connector developed by TNO is open source. The developments carried out by ECI Software Solutions are not open-source.
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The connector is used for the exchange of order related data between manufacturing, installation and construction companies and with wholesalers
Deployment options	Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » via OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes

⁴⁴ <https://www.tno.nl/en/technology-science/technologies/international-data-spaces/>

Usage Control Policies	IDS Connector
Communication	
Communication protocol	IDS-REST
Transfer protocol	Information not available
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	No
Type	-
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker:	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.8 Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) – Framework

Connector Overview

Name	Eclipse Dataspace Components – Framework
Maintainer	Committer Group in Eclipse Foundation
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	<p>Whatever the individual setup is – on-premises bare-metal, different cloud vendors, hybrid, even single end-user machines – the EDC can be customized to work within any environment at scale. The to be build connector's added value is achieved through the separation of control and data plane, enabling a modular and thereby customizable way to build data spaces. Due to common interfaces and mapping of existing standards, the connector adds capabilities of contract negotiating and policy handling in an interoperable manner. As an open-source project hosted by the Eclipse Foundation, it provides a growing list of modules for many widely deployed cloud environments out-of-the-box and can easily be extended for more customized environments, while avoiding any IP right headaches.</p> <p>The EDC are a framework to build connectors but cannot be used as standalone connector implementation.</p>
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Source code repository of the EDC connector⁴⁵ » EDC homepage⁴⁶

Connector Details

Type	Data connector framework
Maturity	TRL 8-9
Portability	Java-based environment required ⁴⁷
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Several data space projects (e.g. Catena-X, Eona-X, mobility Data Space-MDS, Omega-X...) and connector implementations (e.g. Health-X DataLOFT connector, soivity's EDC, Cofinity-X connector)
Deployment options	Not specified

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>

⁴⁶ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Samples/blob/main/basic/basic-01-basic-connector/README.md>

Service level	Framework to build services. Service level is best effort of the open-source-community
Access & Usage Control	
Access control	No
Type of access control	Subject of Data Planes
Support of Usage Control	No, subject to data planes
Usage Control Policies	
Communication	
Communication Protocol	» Dataspace protocol 2024-01 (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added and not part of EDC)
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management provided	No
Type	-
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.9 EdgeDS Connector

Connector Overview

Name	EdgeDS Connector
Maintainer	Intracom Telecom
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The connector is based on the open-source Dataspace Connector by Fraunhofer ISST. It has been adapted to be incorporated within a MEC Platform for Edge Computing applications, therefore combining the IDS capabilities and the ETSI Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) Architectural Framework.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » EdgeDS Github⁴⁸ » Paper "EdgeDS: Data Spaces enabled Multi-access Edge Computing"⁴⁹

Connector Details

Type	off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL 4
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The connector is employed in the Edge Data Space featured on IDSA's Data Space Radar. It demonstrates the advantages of data-driven collaboration among systems and stakeholders through an illustrative use case from the Autonomous Driving field. This scenario envisions various situations for autonomous, connected vehicles on a highway, leveraging advanced safety, traffic routing, and other capabilities via data service ecosystems. E.g. consider a 'see-through' case where a vehicle aims to overtake a truck and temporarily gains access to a video stream from the leading car equipped with a camera. These scenarios extend to 'platooning,' where vehicles can drive in a synchronized manner, sharing sensor data, or the exchange of safety and traffic alerts between highway vehicles.
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud » IoT/CPS/OT devices

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/jkalogero/EdgeDS>

⁴⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.05966>

Service level	Connector as a service
Access & Usage Control	
Access control	Yes
Type of access control	API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	IDS Connector
Communication	
Communication Protocol	Dataspace Protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	No
Type	-
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	As the DSC 8.0.2, the EdgeDS connector uses the IDS Messaging library ⁵⁰ which implements Info Model 4.2.7
Vocabulary	
Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary Provided	IDS Information Model
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	MEC Service Registry
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

⁵⁰ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-Messaging-Services>

2.1.10 EGI DataHub Connector

Connector Overview

Name	EGI DataHub Connector
Maintainer	EGI Foundation
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The EGI DataHub Connector is based on the Dataspace Connector available open source. Policy based access via IDS to multiple storage backends supported by EGI DataHub (e.g. S3, Swift, NFS, GlusterFS, etc). The EGI DataHub is a high-performance data management solution that offers unified data access across globally distributed environments and multiple types of underlying storage, allowing users to share, collaborate and perform computations on the stored data easily.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » EGI DataHub Website⁵¹ » DataHub documentation⁵²

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solutions
Maturity	TRL 4-5
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open-source
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	EUHubs4Data
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » IDS Connector

⁵¹ <https://www.egi.eu/service/datahub/>

⁵² <https://docs.egi.eu/users/data/management/datahub/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Security Level » Application inside a Connector
Usage Control Policies (cont.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » User Role » Time Interval » Duration » Location » Purpose

Communication

Communication Protocol	IDS Multipart
Transfer Protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For management

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	4.2.7

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	IDS Metadata Broker
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.11 EONA-X EDC Connector

Connector Overview

Name of the connector	EONA-X EDC Connector
Maintainer	Amadeus
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	EONA-X EDC Connector allows to connect participants in the domain of Mobility, Transport and Tourism.
More Information	EONA-X website ⁵³

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service » An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	Production grade
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<p>EONA-X EDC connector is deployed by EONA-X participants involved in Paris 2024 Olympics, supporting data exchanges required to support handling delegations during arrival and departure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accreditations - Coordination with local mobility actors, to dispatch athletes - Handling of baggage
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
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⁵³ www.eona-x.eu

Type of access control	OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs)
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-
Communication	
Communication protocol	Dataspace Protocol 2024-01 (HTTPS)
Transfer protocol	In-band with not determined protocol bindings
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Decentralized (did:web)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker:	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	EDC Federated Catalog ⁵⁴
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

⁵⁴ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/FederatedCatalog>

2.1.12 FIWARE Data Space Connector

Connector Overview

Name	FIWARE Data Space Connector
Maintainer	FIWARE Foundation
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Highly modular and scalable Data Space Connector following DSBA Technical Convergence recommendation ⁵⁵
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Documentation⁵⁶ » Source code⁵⁷

Connector Details

Type	Generic and modular open-source solution
Maturity	TRL 6-7
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (MIT)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Used to connect participants in the DOME Marketplace⁵⁸ project » Experiments from i4Trust acceleration program⁵⁹
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Attribute-based access control (ABAC) following an XACML P*P architecture⁶⁰ where attributes of users map to claims in their VCs
Support of Usage Control	Yes

⁵⁵ https://data-spaces-business-alliance.eu/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/Data-Spaces-Business-Alliance-Technical-Convergence-V2.pdf

⁵⁶ <https://github.com/FIWARE/data-space-connector>

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/FIWARE-Ops/data-space-connector>

⁵⁸ <https://dome-marketplace.eu/>

⁵⁹ <https://i4trust.org/experiments/>

⁶⁰ https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=xacml

Usage Control Policies	Data inside the connector can be safeguarded within a Context Broker deployed inside to which only applications, deployed within the connector and owning VCs as specified in usage policies can access data for processing.
Communication	
Communication protocol	HTTPS
Transfer protocol	HTTPS (NGSI-LD)
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » No central control plane » UI for parts of the system: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Credentials Management ○ On-Boarding ○ Acquisition of rights to use products (BAE Marketplace⁶¹)
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Decentralized (based on Decentralized Identifiers ⁶² and Verifiable Credentials ⁶³). Supporting SIOPv2 ⁶⁴ and OIDC4VP ⁶⁵ for authentication.
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	Planned
Type of vocabulary provided	Supports multiple dataspace specific vocabularies compatible based on Smart Data Models ⁶⁶ and others. Description of resources accessible through the connector following DCAT-AP/DCAT
Integration	

⁶¹ <https://github.com/FIWARE-TMForum/Business-API-Ecosystem>

⁶² <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>

⁶³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vc-data-model/>

⁶⁴ https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-self-issued-v2-1_0.html#name-cross-device-self-issued-op

⁶⁵ https://openid.net/specs/openid-4-verifiable-presentations-1_0.html#request_scope

⁶⁶ <https://smartdatamodels.org/>

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker:	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Catalogs based on TMForum-APIs » Data Publication platforms (e.g., CKAN) using DCAT/DCAT-AP
Integration with Clearing House:	Yes
Clearing House type	Gaia-X Digital Clearing Houses (GXDCH)

2.1.13 GATE Dataspace Connector

Connector Overview

Name	GATE Dataspace Connector
Maintainer	GATE Institute
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	<p>GATE Dataspace connector is based on IDS reference implementation and is fully integrated with other components of IDS RAM, namely the Identity provider, the Metadata Broker, the Clearing House, the Vocabulary Hub and the App Store. Digital identities of interacting components are used to ensure trustful message exchange. The connector supports provision of resources via static values, files, APIs and databases. It implements various policies for data usage and follows the negotiation process required for establishing data sharing between two participants. The accompanying UI provides a better user experience with comprehensive functionality for data exchange, metadata search and data application usage.</p>
More Information	GATE Institute GitHub repository ⁶⁷

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic open-source solutions » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service » An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	TRL 5
Portability	Specific
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	Yes (Connector Certification – Checklist Approach) ⁶⁸
Adoption examples	

⁶⁷ <https://github.com/gate-institute/DataspaceConnector/blob/main/LICENSE>

⁶⁸ IDSA news article: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/ids-certification-for-gate-dataspace-connector-our-focus-now-is-on-building-trust-and-expanding-the-ecosystem/>

Deployment options	On-premises
Service level	Platform as a service
Access & Usage Control	
Access control	Yes
Type of access control	» OAuth » Basic auth
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	» IDS Connector » Security Level » Time Interval » Duration » Number of usage » Log Data Usage Information
Communication	
Communication Protocol	» IDS Multipart » IDS protocol (IDSCP)
Transfer Protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	Yes
Type	For users
Identity Management	
Identity management provided	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	Supported Info Model versions: Inbound: "4.0.0", "4.1.0", "4.1.2", "4.2.0", "4.2.1", "4.2.2", "4.2.3", "4.2.4", "4.2.5", "4.2.6", "4.2.7". Outbound: "4.2.7";
Vocabulary	
Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	vocabularies can be added using the Vocabulary Hub
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes

Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	IDS Metadata Broker
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	IDS Clearing House

2.1.14 GDSO Connector - Tyre Information Service

Connector Overview

Name	GDSO Connector - Tyre Information Service
Maintainer	GDSO - Global Data Service Organisation for tyres and automotive components
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Communication protocol based on a rest API with a vocabulary made of standardized data set for all GDSO Members, the meta data broker is a resolver that provides information about the endpoints offered by GDSO Members. Data usage policies allow also to initiate the B2B contract negotiation between GDSO Members and Data users by connecting the parties, but to be managed and finalized outside GDSO.
More Information	GDSO website ⁶⁹

Connector Details

Type	A generic solutions software
Maturity	Live - TRL 9
Portability	Agnostic
License	Partially open source. Proprietary source code that through the REST API can be integrated directly into an IT-Landscape and connected to services. The API is made freely available, but the terms of use do not allow to change it. For GDSO members, one implementation code is also available.
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The connector is adopted by different stakeholders along the tyre value chain: tyre manufacturers, vehicle manufacturers, distributors and others.
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud » IoT/CPS/OT devices
Service level	Platform as a service (i.e., configuration)

⁶⁹ <https://gdso.org/Members-description/Technical-documentation>

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	Data Consumer

Communication

Communication Protocol	REST API
Transfer Protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical User Interface	No
Type	-

Identity Management

Identity management provided	Yes
Type	Centralized based on AWS Cognito

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	Self-developed, called data referential

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	Resolver, storing information about the data endpoints offered by GDSO Members
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.15 HEALTH-X dataLOFT EDC

Connector Overview

Name:	HEALTH-X dataLOFT EDC
Maintainer	Fraunhofer ISST
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The HEALTH-X dataLOFT EDC is an extended and configured version of the EDC Connector. It has been extended in order to realize specific use cases from the healthcare domain.
More Information	HEALTH-X dataLOFT website ⁷⁰

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic solution » An off-the-shelf solution provided as a service » An off-the-shelf solution directly usable integrated in data-related products <p>The connector is used as a generic solution by some project partners, who are building extensions on top of the connector to enable specific use cases. The connector is also an "off-the-shelf" solution, offered as a service in the cloud, or self-hosted by other project partners that want to deploy the connector in their own infrastructure.</p>
Maturity	Use-case specific approach (work in progress)
Portability	Agnostic
License	Has not been finally determined yet, probably open-source in the future (Apache 2.0).
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Within HEALTH-X dataLOFT project
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Self-service » Connector as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
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⁷⁰ <https://www.health-x.org/en/home>

Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Access to the Connector API endpoints secured via API key (provided by the EDC Core) » Access to data assets restricted by matching identity claims inside a user's Verifiable Credential against ODRL policies defined for a given asset (ABAC)
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-
Communication	
Communication Protocol	Dataspace protocol 0.8 (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	No specific GUI has been implemented yet, but the EDC DataDashboard could be used for management/administration
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management provided	Yes
Type	Decentralized (SSI)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	Currently integration with project-specific Federated Catalog implementation that offers Participant Self-Descriptions via REST interface; planned integration with GXFS Federated Catalog.
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.16 IIOC IoT Connector

Connector Overview

Name	IIOC IoT Connector (Intel IONOS Orbiter Connector)
Maintainer	truzzt
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	IoT Version of IDS Connector – compatible to EDC, Extra resource-saving executable for sensors and small devices, Rust & C based
More Information	Not available

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic open-source solutions » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	The connector is already live and usable
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	truzzt Box
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Cloud » IoT/CPS/OT devices
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	API key
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Multipart » Dataspace protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	» for users » for management » for administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Decentralized (SSI)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	4.x
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	Base Camp Federated Catalogue
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	Base Camp Clearing House

2.1.17 Kharon IDS Connector powered by the Dataspace Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Kharon IDS Connector powered by the Dataspace Connector
Maintainer	HOLONIX SRL
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The connector is embedded with a complete IoT asset management solution backed called Kharon. IoT data and augmented intelligence results are now manageable through IDS thanks to the integration of the Kharon solution with the Dataspace Connector; this enables companies to enlarge their IoT network interacting with other device providers and users in a secure way keeping sovereignty and industrial confidentiality.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Holonix website⁷¹ » Dat4Zero project website⁷²

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » generic solution (proprietary software) » off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL 7
Portability	Specific
License	Closed source
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Kharon platform » Dat4Zero project European project (G.A.958363)
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
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⁷¹ <https://www.holonix.it/en/>

⁷² <https://dat4zero.eu/work-packages/>

Type of access control	OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs)
Support of Usage Control	Yes, in Kharon, not implemented in the connector as today
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

Communication Protocol	IDS-REST
Transfer Protocol	In-band with not determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For management

Identity Management

Identity management supported	It's centralized for Kharon, under development for the connector.
Type	-

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.18 Mitsubishi Electric Dataspace Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Mitsubishi Electric Dataspace Connector
Maintainer	Mitsubishi Electric Europe B.V. - German Branch
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Connect an iQ-R PLC system via the Mitsubishi Electric Dataspace Connector running on an RD55UP-12-V module or use the connector on a Mitsubishi Electric industrial PC of the MELIPC Series.
More Information	-

Connector Details

Type	An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	Early stage / Sandbox Stage
Portability	Specific
License	» Open source (Apache License 2.0) ⁷³ » Closed source (modifications, extensions and PLC specific adaptations are not publicly available)
IDS Certification	-
Adoption examples	RD55UP12-V: Proof of concept executed together with the company NTT. It was finished September 2023.
Deployment options	IoT devices. It is possible to execute it on the Mitsubishi Electric C Intelligent Function Module RD55UP12-V (module installed in a PLC system) or on a Mitsubishi Electric industrial PC of the MELIPC Series.
Service level	Self-service. The connector can be installed on the Mitsubishi Electric C Intelligent Function Module RD55UP12-V or on a Mitsubishi Electric industrial PC of the MELIPC Series.

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	» Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password) » The communication is secured with a password

⁷³ The connector is based on the open-source EDC. The EDC repository (<https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>) has been forked to <https://github.com/huebl/DataSpaceConnector> and <https://github.com/huebl/DataSpaceConnector2>.

Support of Usage Control	The communication can be restricted to certain IP addresses, which is enforced by our IT department independent from the connector.
Usage Control Policies	» IDS Connector » Duration
Communication	
Communication Protocol	RD55UP12-V: » Control Plane: IDS Communication Protocol version 4.1.3 » Data Plane: Own developed communication protocol MELIPC: » Control and Data Plane: Dataspace Protocol 0.8
Transfer Protocol	HTTP
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	No (i.e. the connector can only be used via command line or operator needs to develop their own GUI)
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	No
Type	-
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.19 MPAD-C by Mondragon

Connector Overview

Name	MPAD-C by Mondragon
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer	Mondragon Unibertsitatea
Peculiarity of the connector	<p>The connector is included in an architecture that provides a data space that allows MONDRAGON industrial cooperatives to use data for the execution of advanced data analytics, Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms and interoperability between assets and IoT-platforms.</p> <p>This enables companies to overcome a typical challenge in anomaly detection: the technologies and tools for anomaly detection are often not available within the company itself and 3rd party experts and algorithms are required to analyze this data. The IDS Connector assures that this data is used only by the desired company agreeing to the terms established in the contract.</p>
More Information	

Connector Details

Type	A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions)
Maturity	TRL 5
Portability	Agnostic
License	<p>Closed source.</p> <p>The connector is based on the Dataspace Connector originally developed by Fraunhofer ISST⁷⁴. This Mondragon implementation adds components to interoperate with it but these components are not open.</p>
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Qu4lity project⁷⁵ » Local pilot at Mondragon. More information will be made available in the paper on the first European Symposium on Artificial Intelligence in Manufacturing ESAIM2023 (Germany)⁷⁶
Deployment options	On-premises
Service level	Self-service

⁷⁴ More information in 2.2.1

⁷⁵ <https://qu4lity-project.eu/>

⁷⁶ <https://link.springer.com/book/9783031574955>

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	Basic Auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of usage control	Yes
Usage control policies	Usage control policies provided by the Dataspace Connector

Communication

Communication protocol	Leveraging the Dataspace Connector: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Multipart » IDS Communication protocol (IDSCP)
Transfer protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Graphical interface from the open-source Dataspace Connector » Additional node-RED component
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » For users » For management » For administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	V4.0.0

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	IDS Metadata Broker
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.20 OneNet Connector

Connector Overview

Name	OneNet Connector
Maintainer	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.a. and EUROPEAN DYNAMICS Luxembourg S.A.
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » The OneNet Connector, based on TRUE Connector, aims to enable a European Energy Data Space, combining the IDS principles with the advantages of the FIWARE ecosystem ensuring a seamless and secure data exchange in a completely end-to-end decentralized approach. The main features of the OneNet Connector are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Ready-to-go, ready to be installed in any environment and integrated with existing platforms via APIs » Fully integrated with the FIWARE Context Broker (in the NGSI-LD version) » Offers a rich graphical user Interface for connector's configuration and for a series of additional services (KPI's, data exchange timeline, cross-platform services catalogue, vocabularies, etc.) » Facilitates through the GUI or via API the data exchange process, and extends the interaction between data producer/consumer by providing an "offered service" handshake and publish/subscribe mechanisms, accordingly » Integrates data harmonization tool for supporting and mapping CIM standards into NGSI/LD » Can be integrated with third-party Identity Management Services » Supports more than 60 different harmonized services and data profiles in the smart grid and energy field, but can be easily extended with additional services also in other domains » Is completely integrated with the OneNet » Orchestration Workbench and OneNet Monitoring and Analytics Dashboard, two additional tools that allows participants to deploy and evaluate their own services on data coming from the OneNet system and integrate it with analytics and data visualization.
More Information	OneNet project website ⁷⁷

⁷⁷ <https://onenet-project.eu/>

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solution
Maturity	TRL 7 (status Aug. 2023). The OneNet Connector was deployed and tested in 12 different European countries' environments, within the OneNet Demonstration phase. The target TRL at the end of the project is 8.
Portability	Agnostic
License	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Open-source » Open-source – copyleft » Upon project conclusion, it will be open-source under a GPLv3 or similar license.
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Information not available
Deployment options	On-premises
Service level	Connector as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » IDS Connector » Time Interval » Duration » Log Data Usage Information » Inform a participant about the Data Usage

Communication

Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Multipart » IDS Communication Protocol (IDSCP)
Transfer Protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » For users

- » For management
- » For administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	Information not available

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	Fraunhofer Clearing House

2.1.21 Prometheus-X Dataspace Connector

Connector Overview

Name of the connector	Prometheus-X Dataspace Connector
Maintainer	Prometheus-X
Logo of the connector or company logo	PROMETHEUS-X
Peculiarity of the connector	The Prometheus-X Dataspace Connector takes ideas and concepts from IDSA & the Dataspace Protocol, as well as Gaia-X's Trust Framework. In addition, it also offers management of consent and management of personal data.
More Information	Prometheus-X GitHub ⁷⁸ , IDSA blog article ⁷⁹

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solutions
Maturity	TRL 5
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (MIT)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Use cases in Skills (Korean students being matched with Job offers in Europe). More information will be provided in the next versions of this Report.
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Basic auth » API key
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » IDS Connector

⁷⁸ <https://github.com/Prometheus-X-association/dataspace-connector/blob/main/docs/OVERVIEW.md>

⁷⁹ IDSA blog article (June 2024): <https://internationaldataspaces.org/prometheus-x-personalized-learning-and-data-sovereignty-in-education/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » User Role » Location of usage » Purpose » Time Interval » Duration » Number of usage » Delete Data » Log Data Usage Information » User's consent » Data Anonymization (planned)
Communication	
Communication protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS-REST » Dataspace protocol (HTTPS) » Dataspace Protocol (other binding)
Transfer protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical User Interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes (in progress)
Type	Decentralized (did:web)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Type of vocabulary provided	Information not available
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker:	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	Prometheus-X Catalogue
Integration Clearing House	No, but planned

Clearing House type

| GXDCH

2.1.22 Silicon Economy EDC

Connector Overview

Name	Silicon Economy EDC
Maintainer	Fraunhofer ISST
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The connector is developed for the needs of the Silicon Economy. The connector is based on the EDC framework.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » GitLab repository⁸⁰ » Silicon Economy project website⁸¹

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solution
Maturity	TRL 3
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Open Logistics License)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	There is no usage of the connector. Use cases in the logistics domain are being discussed within the silicon economy for the use of the connector.
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud » IoT/CPS/OT devices
Service level	» Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	No
Type of access control	-
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

Communication Protocol	Dataspace Protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	HTTP

⁸⁰ <https://git.openlogisticsfoundation.org/silicon-economy/base/ids/silicon-economy-edc>

⁸¹ <https://www.silicon-economy.com/>

User Interface

Graphical user interface	No
Type	-

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Information not available
Type	-

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.23 soivity CaaS (Connector-as-a-Service)

Connector Overview

Name	soivity CaaS (Connector-as-a-Service)
Maintainer	soivity GmbH
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Fully managed ready-to-use connector based on EDC for easy data sharing between data space participants with usage control and other enhanced usability features. Compatible with data spaces like MDS, Catena-X and more. An integrated API Wrapper provides enhanced endpoints for workflows and improved performance in comparison to default EDC Management API.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » soivity website⁸² » soivity LinkedIn⁸³ » soivity YouTube⁸⁴

Connector Details

Type	Off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL 9, used in production
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Catena-X⁸⁵ » Omega-X⁸⁶ » Mobility Data Space⁸⁷ » Sm4rtenance⁸⁸ (soon)
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud » Others
Service level	» Connector as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
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⁸² <https://soivity.de/en/connect-to-data-space-en/>

⁸³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/soivity>

⁸⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@soivitygmbh>

⁸⁵ <https://catena-x.net/de/>

⁸⁶ <https://omega-x.eu/>

⁸⁷ <https://mobility-dataspace.eu/>

⁸⁸ <https://sm4rtenance.eu/>

Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth 2.0 » Basic Auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password) » API Key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<p>IDS policy classes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector Restriction » Time Interval <p>Additional Catena-X-specific policy classes⁸⁹:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » BusinessPartnerNumber » BusinessPartnerGroup » Membership » FrameworkAgreement » Dismantler
Communication	
Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Dataspace Protocol 0.8 (HTTPS) » Dataspace Protocol 1.0 (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Out-of-band
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes, protected with user accounts (OAuth2)
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » for users » for management » for administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized DAPS (X.509)⁹⁰ » Decentralized (did:web) » Decentralized (SSI)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

⁸⁹ <https://catenax-ev.github.io/docs/standards/CX-0016-CompanyAttributeVerification#24-dismantler-credentials>

⁹⁰ Compatible with AISEC DAPS or sovity DAPS available at <https://github.com/sovity/sovity-daps>

Vocabulary

Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	DCAT, ODRL, DSpace

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	<ul style="list-style-type: none">» EDC's built-in catalogue (all versions)» IDS Broker supported (< v5.0.0)» EDC-based Broker with auto-crawling⁹¹ (all versions)» Catena-X Digital Twin Registry⁹²
Integration with Clearing House:	Yes
Clearing House type	<ul style="list-style-type: none">» IDS Clearing House supported (< v5.0.0)» EDC-based Logging House

⁹¹ <https://github.com/soivity/edc-ce/tree/main/extensions/catalog-crawler>

⁹² <https://github.com/eclipse-tractusx/sldt-digital-twin-registry/tree/main/docs>

2.1.24 soivity Open-Source EDC Connector

Connector Overview

Name	soivity Open-Source EDC Connector
Maintainer	soivity GmbH
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Ready to use open-source connector for easy sharing of data between data space participants with usage control and other enhanced usability features. An integrated API Wrapper provides enhanced endpoints for workflows and improved performance in comparison to default EDC Management API.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Documentation⁹³ » Source code⁹⁴ » Connector UI⁹⁵

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A generic open-source solution » An off-the-shelf solution » A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions)
Maturity	TRL 9, used in production.
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Omega-X⁹⁶ » Sm4rtenance⁹⁷ (soon) » MESEO⁹⁸ (soon) » Mobility Data Space⁹⁹
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud » Others
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Self-Hosted

⁹³ <https://edc.docs.sovity.de>

⁹⁴ <https://github.com/soivity/edc-ce>

⁹⁵ <https://github.com/soivity/edc-ui>

⁹⁶ <https://omega-x.eu/>

⁹⁷ <https://sm4rtenance.eu/>

⁹⁸ <https://meseoproject.eu/>

⁹⁹ <https://mobility-dataspace.eu/>

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface) » Others
Support of usage control	Yes
Usage control policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector Restriction » Time Interval

Communication

Communication protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Dataspace Protocol 0.8 (HTTPS) » Dataspace Protocol 1.0 (HTTPS) - soon
Transfer protocol	Out-of-band

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » for users » for management » for administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized DAPS (X.509)¹⁰⁰ » Mock IAM

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	Yes
Type of vocabulary provided	DCAT, ODRL, DSpace

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
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¹⁰⁰ Compatible with AISEC DAPS or soivity DAPS available at <https://github.com/soivity/soivity-daps>

Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	<ul style="list-style-type: none">» EDC's built-in catalogue (all versions)» IDS Broker supported (< v5.0.0)» EDC-based Broker with auto-crawling¹⁰¹ (all versions)
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	<ul style="list-style-type: none">» IDS Clearing house supported (< v5.0.0)» EDC-based Logging House

¹⁰¹ <https://github.com/sovity/edc-ce/tree/main/extensions/catalog-crawler>

2.1.25 TANGO Connector

Connector Overview

Name	TANGO Connector
Maintainer	Consortium of the TANGO project
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The TANGO Connector enhances the FIWARE Dataspace Connector by replacing the existing PDP/PEP modules with its own advanced modules, designed to evaluate the trustworthiness and behavior of requesters during the access request process. This evaluation is conducted using attribute-based policies and a range of trustworthiness scores. Additionally, TANGO integrates CP-ABE encryption, adding a robust encryption layer to secure the data exchanged through the connector.
More Information	The repository of the TANGO connector is not available to the public. Please find here more information on the 2.1.12 FIWARE Data Space Connector.

Connector Details

Type	A data connector framework
Maturity	TRL 6
Portability	Specific
License	Partially open source. The FIWARE Dataspace Connector is open source. The TANGO developments are not.
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The connector is being implemented in some of the project use cases. More information on the TANGO website ¹⁰²
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs)
Support of Usage Control	Yes

¹⁰² TANGO project website: <https://tango-project.eu/>

Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » User Role
Communication	
Communication Protocol	The connector uses HTTPS REST APIs for communication between the individual components
Transfer Protocol	In-band with not determined protocol bindings
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Decentralized (did:web) » Decentralized (SSI)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.26 Tech2B SCSN Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Tech2B SCSN Connector
Maintainer	Tech2B
Logo of the connector or company logo	

Peculiarity of the connector	Enabling data spaces for SMEs
More Information	Via the Tech2B AppStore for industry-specific applications, allowing one-click expansion of the Tech2B's core features and enabling data spaces for SMEs

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service » An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	TRL 7-8
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Smart Connected Supplier Network » Market 4.0 » Example use cases: 1on1 transactions: Share daily order transactions with suppliers that have none or an outdated software system. Standardized, secure and easy to use for companies without digitization knowledge, to build a future-proof and connected supply chain. Supply & Demand: Enable the opportunity for buyers to use the reach of our network in the quotation phase. Our service provider acts as proxy to place incoming RFQ on Tech2B Supply & Demand and return quotations directly to the buyer.
Deployment options	Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	Number of usages

Communication

Communication Protocol	Dataspace Protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Information not available

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	» for users » for management » for administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Decentralized (did:web)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.27 Tekniker Dataspace Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Tekniker Dataspace Connector
Maintainer	Tekniker
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Modular solution that allows companies to establish a single point of entry to the data offered and requested through a data space ensuring interoperability at data sharing, trust between the parties involved in data sharing and data sovereignty throughout its life-cycle.
More Information	

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solutions
Maturity	TRL 7
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (CC BY NC ND)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Construction Data Space for Building Permit Management (DigiChecks project ¹⁰³)
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud » Edge
Service level	Connector as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	SSI
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Restrict the data usage to a group of users » Restrict the data usage to specific locations » Log the data usage information

Communication

¹⁰³ <https://digichecks.eu/>

Communication Protocol	Dataspace Protocol 2024-01 (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For users
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	SSI
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	Dataspace Information Model from Dataspace Protocol 2024-01
Vocabulary	
Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	ifcOWL and others depending on the Vocabulary Hub
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

2.1.28 Telekom DIH Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Telekom DIH Connector
Maintainer	T-Systems International GmbH
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Connect to any dataspace in less than 5 minutes and start sharing data through one of the first IDS certified, Gaia-X compliant, cloud agnostic, plug-and-play connectors. We remove technical configuration complexities and provide an easier and user-friendly way for trusted data exchange, with sovereignty protection.
More Information	Data Intelligence Hub website ¹⁰⁴

Connector Details

Type	An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	TRL 9
Portability	Cloud - Agnostic
License	Closed source
IDS Certification	Yes (Connector Certification - Concept Review ¹⁰⁵)
Adoption examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data chains in Catena-X » Traceability applications in Catena-X » Research use-cases in Gaia-X 4 Future Mobility
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Connector as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	IDS policy classes:

¹⁰⁴ <https://dih.telekom.com/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/t-systems-and-idsa-achieve-milestone-for-data-spaces-first-certification-of-a-connector-promotes-standardization-and-interoperability/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » User Role » Time Interval » Duration » Location » Purpose <p>Additional Catena-X-specific policy classes¹⁰⁶:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> » BusinessPartnerNumber » Membership » BusinessPartnerGroup » FrameworkAgreement » Dismantler
Communication	
Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Dataspace Protocol 0.8 (HTTPS) – production-ready » Dataspace Protocol 2024-01 (HTTPS) – production-ready
Transfer Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added) » Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » for users » for management » for administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized (X.509) » Decentralized (did:web)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	4.2.0

¹⁰⁶ <https://catenax-ev.github.io/docs/standards/CX-0016-CompanyAttributeVerification#24-dismantler-credentials>

Vocabulary

Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	Supports multiple dataspace specific vocabularies

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker Type	» Federated Catalogue » IDS based Meta Data Broker
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	Supports integration with Gaia-X Digital Clearing House

2.1.29 TNO Security Gateway (TSG)

Connector Overview

Name	TNO Security Gateway (TSG)
Maintainer	TNO
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Multi-purpose connector
More Information	GitLab repository ¹⁰⁷

Connector Details

Type	A generic open-source solution
Maturity	TRL 8
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source
IDS Certification	Yes (Connector Certification - Concept Review) ¹⁰⁸
Adoption examples	SCSN ¹⁰⁹ - actively used in production. Different European and Dutch projects.
Deployment options	Cloud
Service level	Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » Security Level » Time Interval » Location » Number of usages

¹⁰⁷ <https://tno-tsg.gitlab.io/>

¹⁰⁸ https://www.tno.nl/en/newsroom/2024/03/data-spaces-certification/?utm_source=linkedin&utm_medium=social&utm_content=ISP&utm_term=TNO+digitaal

¹⁰⁹ <https://smart-connected-supplier-network.gitbook.io/processmanual/>

Communication

Communication Protocol	IDS Multipart
Transfer Protocol	IDS Multipart

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	» for users » for management » for administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	4.1.0

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	Metadata Broker Open Core ¹¹⁰
Integration with Clearing House	Not yet
Clearing House type	-

¹¹⁰ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/metadata-broker-open-core>

2.1.30 Tritom Enterprise Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Tritom Enterprise Connector
Maintainer	DataSpace Europe Oy
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Enables data source and target systems technical connectivity to the Tritom service to produce services based on data sovereignty principles. Tritom also brings together ecosystem parties and provides the capabilities to create data and service catalogues.
More Information	Tritom website ¹¹¹

Connector Details

Type	An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	Used in the Tritom service current version, TRL8
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source, Tritom Enterprise license
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	In the Tritom service licensed by DataSpace Europe Oy
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

Communication Protocol	REST
Transfer Protocol	Information not available

¹¹¹ <https://www.dataspace.fi/en/data-intermediation-service>

User Interface

Graphical user interface	No
Type	-

Identity Management

Identity management supported	No
Type	-

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No, the connector is agnostic to content
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-
Additional Comments	Our Tritom service is in version 1.0 and is being still developed.

2.1.31 TRUE Connector

Connector Overview

Name	TRUE Connector
Maintainer	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SpA
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The TRUE Connector enables the trusted data exchange in order to be an active part of an IDS Ecosystem, a virtual data space leveraging existing standards and technologies, as well as governance models well accepted in the data economy, to facilitate secure and standardized data exchange and data linkage in a trusted business ecosystem. The TRUE connector is also part of the Fiware Catalogue: the integration of existing Fiware ecosystems is guaranteed by the dedicated Data APP, enabling the IDS-based interaction in a plug-and-play way.
More Information	GitHub repository ¹¹²

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector framework » A generic open-source solution
Maturity	TRL 6; Part of the IDSA Graduation Scheme (Sandbox)
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (AGPL version 3) ¹¹³
IDS Certification	Yes (Connector Certification - Concept Review)
Adoption examples	Several research projects (Market4.0, AI Regio, Platoon, Circular TwAIIn, Eur3ka, CLARUS, SCREAM, CiTrace)
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud » IoT/CPS/OT devices
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
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¹¹² <https://github.com/Engineering-Research-and-Development/true-connector>

¹¹³ https://github.com/Engineering-Research-and-Development/true-connector-execution_core_container/blob/master/LICENSE

Type of access control	Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Connector » Security Level » User Role » Time Interval » Duration » Purpose » Number of usages
Communication	
Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Multipart » IDS protocol (IDSCP)
Transfer Protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported Version of IDS Information Model	4.2.7
Vocabulary	
Supported	No, responsibility to manage data is up to the data app
Type of Vocabulary Provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker Type	Fraunhofer Meta Data Broker (5.0.0)
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House Type	Fraunhofer Clearing House from IDSA GitHub repository

2.1.32 Trusted Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Trusted Connector
Maintainer	Fraunhofer AISEC
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Enforceable Usage Control using Trusted Execution Environment integration and Remote Attestation
More Information	GitHub repository ¹¹⁴

Connector Details

Type	A generic solutions software
Maturity	IDS_ready Component, ~ TRL 7
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	None
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Application inside a Connector » Time Interval

Communication

Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Multipart » IDS protocol (IDSCP)
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¹¹⁴ <https://github.com/Fraunhofer-AISEC/trusted-connector>

Transfer Protocol	No
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	For administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	Version 4.1.0
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	AISEC-provided Clearing House

2.1.33 Trusted Supplier Connector

Connector Overview

Name	Trusted Supplier Connector
Maintainer	German Edge Cloud GmbH & Co. KG
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	Usability through Configuration and Monitoring UI, tailored for Cloud, Edge and hybrid scenarios
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » German Edge Cloud website¹¹⁵ » IDSA blog article¹¹⁶

Connector Details

Type	An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	IDS_ready, TRL 8
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source, proprietary / individual
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Fraunhofer HHI, Fraunhofer HHI Digitale Signalverarbeitung, ICNAP IPT-HHI
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service » Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	API key
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

¹¹⁵ <https://gec.io/solutions/gaia-x-dienste/>

¹¹⁶ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/secure-and-trusted-data-exchange-german-edge-clouds-oncite-is-ids-ready/>

Communication Protocol	» IDS Multipart » HTTP, Cloud Events, IDS Header
Transfer Protocol	Database access is handled by provider
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	» for users » for administration
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	No
Type	-
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House Type	-
Additional Comments	We have validated the connector in external research projects and are looking for business customers.

2.1.34 VTT DSIL Connector

Connector Overview

Name	VTT DSIL Connector
Maintainer	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Peculiarity of the connector	The VTT DSIL Connector (DSILC) significantly elevates the capabilities of the Dataspace connector reference implementation by introducing a suite of advanced features. These include support for the OPC UA communication protocol, a robust user and role-based access management system, and a heightened level of security, which includes protection against XSS (Cross-Site Scripting), clickjacking, and DOS (Denial of Service) attacks. Furthermore, we've enforced rigorous validation checks for the connector to ensure its integrity and reliability. In addition, our implementation incorporates enhanced security measures for the Postgres database. The VTT DSIL Connector finds its primary domain of application within the manufacturing sector, where it plays an indispensable role in facilitating seamless data communication while ensuring the utmost security and data resource access integrity.
More Information	Article on VTT Hub Facilitator website ¹¹⁷

Connector Details

Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service » An off-the-shelf solution, directly usable integrated in data-related products
Maturity	IDS Certification
Portability	Agnostic
License	Closed source at the moment. No final decisions for the license have been made.
IDS Certification	Yes (Connector Certification - Concept Review)
Adoption examples	The DSIL connector is being used in several research and development projects. These include TRUSTEE (Trust and Privacy Preserving Computing Platform For Cross-Border Federation Of Data), OSME ¹¹⁸ (Open Smart Manufacturing

¹¹⁷ <https://www.idsa-finland.fi/vtt-has-officially-kicked-off-the-certification-process-for-their-ids-connector/>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.mexfinland.org/osme/>

	Ecosystem) and RESONANCE ¹¹⁹ (Replicable and Efficient Solutions for Optimal Management of Cross-sector Energy).
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Connector as a service » Platform as a service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » Basic auth (Basic access authorization, providing username and password)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » IDS Connector » Security Level » User Role » Time Interval » Duration » Number of usages » Log Data Usage Information » Inform a participant about the Data Usage » Delete Data

Communication

Communication Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » IDS Multipart » IDS protocol (IDSCP) » Dataspace protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	In-band with determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	No
Type	-

Identity Management

¹¹⁹ <https://www.resonance-project.eu/>

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	Yes
Supported version of IDS Information Model	Supported Info Model versions: Outbound: "4.2.7"; Inbound: "4.0.0", "4.1.0", "4.1.2", "4.2.0", "4.2.1", "4.2.2", "4.2.3", "4.2.4", "4.2.5", "4.2.6", "4.2.7".
Vocabulary	
Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	The IDS metadata broker reference implementation ¹²⁰
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

¹²⁰ <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/metadata-broker-open-core>

2.2 Connectors with latest updates in May 2023

This section describes four connectors whose information was provided before May 2023. No updates have been provided since then.

An overview of these four connectors is reported in *Figure 4 Overview of connectors with latest updates in May 2023* below.

Connectors with latest updates in May 2023			
Section	Name of connector	Maintainer	Open source
2.2.1	Dataspace Connector (DSC)		✓
2.2.2	GAIABOX [®] .IDS. BasicConnector	nicos	
2.2.3	TeraLab Connector	TERALAB Data Science for Europe	
2.2.4	WeTech Smart Data Connector		

Figure 4 Overview of connectors with latest updates in May 2023

2.2.1 Dataspace Connector

Name of the connector	Dataspace Connector
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer (company name)	The project is currently no longer maintained but looking for new maintainers ¹²¹
Type of connector	Generic open-source solution
Short description	<p>The Dataspace Connector is an IDS connector that is currently being maintained by sovity. The connector was originally developed at the Fraunhofer ISST.</p> <p>With the help of the Dataspace Connector, existing software can easily be extended by IDS connector functionalities in order to integrate them into an IDS data ecosystem. Furthermore, it is possible to use the Dataspace Connector as a basis for the development of own software that is to be connected to an IDS data ecosystem.</p>
Maturity Level	IDS-Ready and part of the IDS Graduation Scheme
License type	Open source
Features	<p>The Dataspace Connector integrates the IDS Information Model and uses the IDS Messaging Services for IDS functionalities and message handling.</p> <p>The core component in this repository provides a REST API for loading, updating, and deleting resources with local or remote data enriched by its metadata. It supports IDS conform message handling with other IDS connectors and components and implements usage control for selected IDS usage policy patterns.</p>
Adoption	The Dataspace Connector has been used in different projects and it is also part of the IDSA Reference Testbed ¹²²
External resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Project website¹²³ » GitHub repository AI.SOV on the Data Spaces Radar¹²⁴

2.2.2 GAIAboX

Name of the connector	GAIAboX®.IDS. BasicConnector
-----------------------	------------------------------

¹²¹ Updated in April 2024. More information is provided here: <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/DataspaceConnector?tab=readme-ov-file#contributing>

¹²² <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-testbed>

¹²³ <https://international-data-spaces-association.github.io/DataspaceConnector/>

¹²⁴ <https://www.dataspace-radar.org/radar/>

Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer (company name)	nicos AG
Type of connector	Generic solution (proprietary software)
Short description	IDS BasicConnector, based on IDS-G specifications and ready to be equipped with additional protocols and/or application-functionalities.
Maturity Level	Up and running for and in nicos.testbed.IDS, following given IDS Certification criteria for components. Starting with Certification Trust Level 1 – Assurance Level 1 (Checklist Approach) and preparing for next level of certification.
License type	Closed source
Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Uses IDS DAPS as identity provider » Ready for VC/VP » Usage Control (subset of IDS Usage Control, plus superset of well-known access control features) » Aligned to current IDS Information Model (IDS-IM) » Works as a Linked Data Platform (LDP, so aligned to W3C “solid”) » Aims to work with gRPC as an additional (but IDS-aligned) application protocol.
Adoption	Used by nicos.testbed.IDS as “Alice and Bob” Base for “Delegated Access Control Service” (expressed by DACL, the “Dynamic Access Control Language”) Base for Clearing House / Logging Service, too (Linked Data Notification, IDS Multipart Message, etc.).
External resources	Homepage will be provided in the next version of the Report.

2.2.3 Teralab Connector

Name of the connector	TeraLab Connector
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer (company name)	TeraLab
Type of connector	Generic open-source solution
Short description	Test connector used to get familiar with IDS and interact with EUHubs4Data partners. It is based on the Dataspace Connector ¹²⁵ (v8.0.2).
Maturity Level	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
License type	Proprietary
Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » RAM Version: 3.0 » Info Model version: 4.2.7 » Protocol: HTTPS / multipart » Usage Control Capabilities: in line with the Dataspace Connector v8.0.2
Adoption	TeraLab Marketplace: Enabling data to move between the Marketplace and the connector using a back-end server.
External resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » TeraLab Marketplace¹²⁶ » Code repository: internal (protected in a private network) » TeraLab Connector URL¹²⁷

¹²⁵ Dataspace Connector repository: <https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/DataspaceConnector/blob/main/LICENSE>

¹²⁶ <https://marketplace.teralab-datascience.fr/home>

¹²⁷ <https://ws37.tl.teralab-datascience.fr:30089>

2.2.4 WeTech Connector

Name of the connector	WeTech Smart Data Connector
Logo of the connector or company logo	
Maintainer (company name)	WeTech Holding Co., Limited
Type of connector	N.A.
Short description	<p>With the standard data usage strategy and asymmetric encryption technology defined in IDS, this connector achieves safe and reliable data transmission between the data sharing parties, and the implementation of the data provider's policies in the control of data usage time interval, usage times, usage methods and other policies. It can be applied to the sharing, use and control of important official documents, finance data, and market or business opportunities etc. between internal departments of large enterprises.</p> <p>A big tech firm in China has been using the connector, and its reliability has been proven.</p>
Maturity Level	Preparing for IDS Certification (Trust Level 1 Assurance Level 2)
License type	Closed source
Features	Technological stack: Java, IDSCP, Personal Host
Adoption	Cross-border data sharing for a major Chinese telecom operator
External resources	

3 Additional initiatives and promising emerging solutions

In addition to the existing IDS-based data connectors described above, other approaches also support data sharing in data-driven business ecosystems. Due to the diversity of data sharing requirements - ranging from confidentiality and regulatory constraints to technology limitations - there is room for additional initiatives and promising new technologies. To unlock the full potential of the available data, all data-sharing approaches must be interoperable. For these reasons, IDSA is building a global standard for data connectors, gradually incorporating other technologies and concepts. The following additional initiatives and emerging solutions have been identified:

- Axone Protocol¹²⁸ (formerly known as OKP4 Protocol): A domain-specific layer-1 solution dedicated to trust-minimized data sharing. The blockchain technology orchestrates assets shared by participants in the Data verse: data, algorithms, software, storage and computation to enable a new generation of applications. Any contributor earns rewards thanks to these new value chains. More information is provided in Appendix 1: Axone Protocol.
- Ocean Protocol: A comprehensive framework for data services in crypto ecosystems. Based on crypto tokens it provides mechanisms for smart contracts, marketplaces, and compute-to-data. It is available as open source. For more information visit their website¹²⁹.
- Ocean Provider¹³⁰: REST API for provider of data services, and it is part of the Ocean Protocol stack. More information is provided in Appendix 2: Ocean Provider.
- RUN-DSP: An open source go-lang implementation of the IDSA Dataspaces Protocol. More information is available in Appendix 3: RUN-DSP
- DOME 4.0 IDS connector adaptor: A wrapping layer to facilitate easy connections with other solutions and adherence to the DOME API. More information in Appendix 4: DOME 4.0 IDS connector adaptor.

¹²⁸ <https://okp4.network/>

¹²⁹ <https://docs.pontus-x.eu/>

¹³⁰ <https://docs.oceanprotocol.com/developers/provider>

4 Other technologies contributing to trustworthily share data

Data sharing in data spaces is built on more than the use of data connectors in distributed networks. A soft data infrastructure based on centralized or decentralized essential services is the foundation for data sharing. This infrastructure is not just technology put into practice but encompasses a frame for solutions based on the BLOFT thinking (business, legal, operational, functional, technological) that spans across data spaces. Additionally, the type of data - personal or non-personal - affects how it is shared, whether by an organization, a service or an individual. Various initiatives address these aspects. Below are some key examples:

- Gaia-X trust framework¹³¹
- The Eclipse XFSC¹³² (Cross Federation Services Components) formerly known as GXFS
- iShare trust framework¹³³
- MyData Operators¹³⁴
- SOLID¹³⁵

Data connectors and the soft data infrastructure do not aim to reinvent the wheel but to combine common standards and frameworks into a comprehensive solution. Important standards to consider for implementing identity and access management, claim management, data and data contract policies include:

- The W3C Tech Stack:
 - o RDF¹³⁶
 - o ODRL¹³⁷
 - o DCAT¹³⁸

¹³¹ <https://gaia-x.eu/gaia-x-framework/>

¹³² <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.xfsc>

¹³³ <https://ishare.eu/>

¹³⁴ <https://oldwww.mydata.org/mydata-operators/>

¹³⁵ <https://solidproject.org/>

¹³⁶ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

¹³⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

¹³⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

5 Conclusion

The *Data Connector Report* is a comprehensive guide that explains the importance of data connectors, their role in data spaces, and the key factors required to make them interoperable. It also provides a clear and comprehensive overview of the different types of data connectors, their features, and adoption scenarios. Since the September 2023 version, additional technical details such as type of identity management, access control, usage control, supported protocols have been included. These enhancements allow for a more accurate and comprehensive insight of the different connectors, and pave the way for future comparisons, taxonomies, and analysis of their evolution. The Report also showcases other emerging solutions and technologies for data spaces, highlighting the role of IDSA and other relevant initiatives in this context and fostering a shared vision for future alignment and interoperability.

Some exclusive insights can be derived from a first analysis of the information provided in this *Data Connector Report*. One of the key learnings from this Report is the diversity of data connector implementations. Among the 38 connectors evaluated, there is a clear distribution between open-source, partially open-source, and closed-source solutions, with 17 being open-source, 3 partially open, and 18 closed-source. This variety reflects the different priorities and preferences of organizations depending on their needs for flexibility, control, and commercial interests.

Another significant finding is the identification of six major development streams for data connectors:

- 1) Eclipse Dataspace Components Connector, forming the base for 11 different connector variants.
- 2) Dataspace Connector, forming the basis for 9 connector variants.
- 3) TNO Security Gateway (TSG), forming the base for 2 different connectors.
- 4) TRUE Connector, which is the foundation for one additional connector.
- 5) Trusted Connector, which is the basis for one connector.
- 6) FIWARE Dataspace Connector, which forms the foundation for one connector.

Beyond this, the Report contains eight unique variants of data connector implementations.

More information on the development streams is contained in Figure 5 Data connector development streams.

Figure 5 Data connector development streams

In addition to the listed data connectors, five other emerging solutions have been identified, which are not qualified yet as data connectors.

Figure 6 Number of connector variants

The above-listed connectors support different identity management mechanisms based on the information available¹³⁹:

- 17 connectors support X.509
- 7 support did:web
- 6 support SSI
- 3 support other identity management mechanisms
- 8 do not support any identity management

Regarding IDS Certification¹⁴⁰, five data connectors have completed the IDS Certification process:

- Four connectors have been certified via Assurance Level 2 – Concept Review:
 - Telekom DIH Connector by T-Systems (December 2023)
 - VTT DSIL Connector (February 2024)
 - TNO Security Gateway (March 2024)

¹³⁹ The connectors listed in 2.2 Connectors with latest updates in May 2023 do not provide information on identity management

¹⁴⁰ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/certification/>

- TRUE Connector by Engineering (April 2024)
- One connector has been certified via Assurance Level 1 – Checklist approach:
 - GATE Dataspace Connector (September 2024)

The IDS Certification ensures that the connector meets the security and functionality requirements defined by the IDSA Working Group Certification. This milestone marks a significant step towards market-ready data spaces, paving the way towards interoperability and simplifying the end-user experience.

"Witnessing T-Systems, VTT, TNO, Engineering and GATE obtaining the world's first IDS Certification for their IDS Connectors is a momentous occasion. This achievement not only signifies a crucial step in standardizing data spaces but also highlights our dedication to fostering secure, interoperable solutions that contribute to the sustainable development of the data economy."

Sonia Jimenez, Director Data Space Technology | IDSA

The *Data Connector Report* has not only provided detailed insights into existing solutions but has also identified the trends shaping the future of data connectors. The evolution of connectors, along with their certification, signals a maturing market. Furthermore, the recognition of emerging technologies highlights the need for continuous innovation and alignment as data-sharing ecosystems expand.

As the *Data Connector Report* concludes with this edition, it sets the stage for the forthcoming *Data Space Connector Report*, to be published in November, which will focus on connectors supporting the Dataspace Protocol. This upcoming Report will further reinforce IDSA's mission to build a global standard for data sharing and interoperability, aligning technologies and fostering a cohesive vision for data spaces.

For more information and to discover how to support the association's activities, please contact the IDSA head office¹⁴¹. Visit the IDSA website to learn more about becoming a member¹⁴² or offer a donation¹⁴³.

¹⁴¹ info@internationaldataspaces.org

¹⁴² <https://internationaldataspaces.org/we/become-a-member/>

¹⁴³ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/we/donate/>

Appendix 1: Axone Protocol

Solution overview

Name	Axone Protocol
Maintainer	OKP4 Association
Peculiarity	Axone is the protocol used to connect, share, and monetize resources between all AI services. It simplifies AI resource coordination and eliminates the ultimate AI bottleneck: Data. With AXONE, you can train your model using data from multiple sources, with the data owner choosing his level of privacy, from federated learning to open data contributions
More Information	Axone documentation ¹⁴⁴

Solution Details

Type	A generic open-source solutions
Maturity	TRL 6
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2 and BSD 3-Clause)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	None
Deployment options	-
Service level	-

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » Security Level » User Role » User consent » Event » Time Interval » Duration » Number of usages

¹⁴⁴ <https://docs.okp4.network/>

- » Log Data Usage Information
- » Inform a participant about the Data Usage
- » Delete Data

Communication

Communication Protocol	HTTPS
Transfer Protocol	In-band with not determined protocol bindings

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » For users » For management » For administration

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Decentralized (did:web)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	No
Type of Vocabulary provided	-

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	No
Clearing House type	-

Appendix 2: Ocean Provider

Solution overview

Name	Ocean Provider
Maintainer	Ocean Enterprise Collective, deltaDAO AG

Peculiarity	The Ocean Provider is an API exclusively designed as an access controller and proxy controlling access to data services and allowing the orchestration of data product generation processes. Same as other data space connectors it is the component responsible for sovereign data access management. It leverages audit trails and identity management components to decide if a consumer or process shall receive access to a connected resource for further processing or download. The fine-grained access controls provide explicit access control options with the use of access tokens and SSI verifier solutions by means of i.e., a keycloak integration. Only users with valid access tokens and credentials can access certain resources or trigger the orchestration of Compute-to-Data processes. The access controller allows a wide variety of data sources, besides infrastructure and software services for computation. It allows the provisioning of data from static data sources (files), decentralized data sources (IPFS, Arweave), databases and APIs. The Ocean Provider performs encryption/ decryption of the asset metadata, permission checking for consumption flows, data streaming, initiation of Compute-to-Data flows and offers multichain support for any public or private EVM-compatible blockchain network.
More Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Pontus-X documentation¹⁴⁵ » Pontus-X ecosystem¹⁴⁶
Solution Details	
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » A framework » A generic open-source solutions » An off-the-shelf solution, provided as a service
Maturity	TRL Level 8-9 (used in production)
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache License 2.0) ¹⁴⁷
IDS Certification	No
Adoption Examples	Pontus-X Ecosystem, Gaia-X Lighthouses (EuProGigant, Gaia-X 4 Future Mobility, ACCURATE, COOPERANTS) and Projects, AIRBUS Defense and Space Market, XAsia of State Library of Berlin, Acentrik, deltaDAO Marketplace, EnergySHR Energy Data Market, OVAL Open Validation Platform, Flex4Res, Dione-X, Univery de Lleida Agriculture

¹⁴⁵ <https://docs.pontus-x.eu/>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.pontus-x.eu/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://github.com/oceanprotocol/provider/blob/main/LICENSE>

	Data Portal, agrifoodTEF, Future Mobility Marketplace, Dynamo
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Edge » On-premises » Cloud » IoT/CPS/OT devices
Service level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Solution as a service » Platform as a service » Self service
Access & Usage Control	
Access control	Yes
Type	Authorization Token, standard/framework for REST/API
Support of Usage Control	Yes
Usage Control Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Data Consumer » Application inside a Connector » Time Interval » Duration » Purpose » Event » Data Sale Contract » Data Rental Contract » State » Number of usage » Modify Data in Transit » Log Data Usage Information
Communication	
Communication Protocol	Ocean Protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » In-band with determined protocol bindings » Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added)
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » For users » For management » For administration

Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized (X.509) » Decentralized (SSI) » Decentralized (did:web) » Participant Registry, Gaia-X Compliance 22.10, SECP256K1 PKI
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	Freely extensible for domain specific implementations, DCAT, Base-X, Schema.org, Ocean DDOs, Gaia-X Compliance 22.10
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	Yes
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	Ocean Aquarius (meta data), Gaia-X Credential Event Service (CES) for Compliance Credentials, DCAT for data resource meta data, Ocean Subgraph (transactional data), Gaia-X Compliance for participants, services, and resources.
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	Gaia-X Digital Clearing House (GXDCH)

Appendix 3: RUN-DSP

Solution Overview

Name	RUN-DSP
Maintainer	ponc.tech
Peculiarity	run-dsp is an open source go lang implementation of the IDSA dataspace protocol.
More Information	RUN-DSP documentation ¹⁴⁸

Solution details

Type	A generic open-source solutions
Maturity	This is pre-alpha software and will be undergoing several changes
Portability	Agnostic
License	Open source (Apache 2.0)
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	Under evaluation within the HEALTH-X project
Deployment options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » On-premises » Cloud
Service level	Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

Communication Protocol	Dataspace protocol (HTTPS)
Transfer Protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Out-of-band utilizing data planes without determined protocol bindings (data planes to be added)

¹⁴⁸ <https://github.com/go-dataspace/run-dsp>

	» Out-of-band utilizing data planes with protocol bindings (data planes are part of the connector offering)
User Interface	
Graphical user interface	No
Type	-
Identity Management	
Identity management supported	Yes
Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » Centralized (X.509) » Decentralized (SSI) » Decentralized (did:web)
Information Model	
IDS Information Model	-
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-
Vocabulary	
Supported	-
Type of Vocabulary provided	-
Integration	
Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	-
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	-
Clearing House type	-

Appendix 4: DOME 4.0 IDS connector adaptor

Solution Overview

Name	DOME 4.0 IDS connector adaptor
Maintainer	Consortium of DOME 4.0 project
Peculiarity	The solution is a wrapping layer to be able to connect to any online solution and adhere to the DOME API. It can be used to connect IDS-compliant connectors or any web-front end database.
More Information	DOME 4.0 project website ¹⁴⁹

Solution Details

Type	A generic solutions software (proprietary generic solutions)
Maturity	Proof of concept, TRL 4
Portability	Specific
License	Open source (GPL) ¹⁵⁰
IDS Certification	No
Adoption examples	The solution is being implemented in some of the project use cases. In particular, there is a local deployment of the TRUE Connector with the wrapper to the DOME platform.
Deployment options	On-premises
Service level	Self-service

Access & Usage Control

Access control	Yes
Type of access control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » OAuth (Open authorization, standard/framework for REST/APIs) » API key (Manage access through a unique code for programming interface)
Support of Usage Control	No
Usage Control Policies	-

Communication

Communication Protocol	DOME 4.0 protocol ¹⁵¹
Transfer Protocol	DOME 4.0 protocol

¹⁴⁹ <https://dome40.eu/>

¹⁵⁰ <https://github.com/DOME-4-0/reference-connector>

¹⁵¹ <https://github.com/DOME-4-0/reference-connector> and <https://github.com/DOME-4-0/reference-connector/blob/main/Documents/Steps%20to%20create%20a%20connector.pdf>

User Interface

Graphical user interface	Yes
Type	Integrated into the DOME 4.0 platform

Identity Management

Identity management supported	Yes
Type	Centralized (X.509)

Information Model

IDS Information Model	No
Supported version of IDS Information Model	-

Vocabulary

Supported	Yes
Type of Vocabulary provided	DOME 4.0 Data Set Ontology ¹⁵²

Integration

Integration with Catalogue/Meta Data Broker	No
Catalogue/Meta Data Broker type	-
Integration with Clearing House	Yes
Clearing House type	DOME 4.0 Clearing House ¹⁵³

¹⁵² https://dome40.eu/sites/default/files/2022-11/DOME%204.0%20D3.1%20Semantic%20data%20exchange%20ontology%202022.08.05%20PU%20-%20revised_0.pdf

¹⁵³ https://dome40.eu/sites/default/files/2023-06/DOME%204.0%20D2.3%20Data_Sovereignty_and_Provenance_System_2023.05.31.pdf

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